

Construction Students' Thinking in Solving Mathematics Problem Using Cognitive Map

Anton Prayitno¹ and Ni Wayan Suarniati²

^{1,2} Universitas Wisnuwardhana Malang, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education,
Jl. Danau Sentani 99, Malang, Indonesia,

Abstract

This qualitative study was conducted on students of class IX SMP and aims to explore students' thinking in solving mathematics problem were portrayed using a cognitive map. The development of this instrument about decision-making based on the curriculum of junior high. Procedure of data collection begins with subject are asked to work on the issue with think a loud. The results of the work and think a loud of students then analyzed. The results showed that when portrayed using a cognitive map was found that thinking of students in solving mathematics problem are different, as shown by strategy used when solving problems. In addition, research by cognitive maps can be used as a tool to the discover error of students thinking, explore the construction process of understanding students' and explore the characteristics of student thinking.

Keyword: thinking construction, mathematics problem, cognitive map

INTRODUCTION

In this decade, some researchers revealed that a study related to thinking process is important in the study of mathematics education (Prayitno, 2015, 2016; Subanji & Nusantara, 2013). Therefore, students' mathematical thinking ability needs to be developed in learning mathematics in school. On the contrary, this ability is seldom trained or raised by teachers in learning mathematics. The learning process of mathematics used by teachers only rely on the mastery of *basic skill*, procedural ability, rules, and more emphasis on memorization also concerned on the final outcome of the process. In this case, show that teachers are only secure themselves. If there is any material that is considered difficult, teachers may use *pre-memory* techniques and provide exercises as much as possible. In fact, the 2006 and 2013

curriculum showed that teachers need to provide the opportunity for students to develop logical, analytical, systematic, critical, and creative thinking ability, as well as the ability to work together in solving mathematics problem.

As disclosed Yuwono (2009), thinking level achievement of Indonesian students is only 6% who reached the stage of high level thinking, and 1% reached the advanced level thinking. Indonesian students' thinking achievement is on a low level, lower than thinking achievement of Singapore students (77% reached high level thinking and 44% reached the advanced level thinking and Malaysian students (30% reached the stage of high level thinking and 6% reached the advanced level thinking). In addition, on the international study TIMSS 2011 (Subanji & Nusantara, 2013), the achievement of 8 grader in mathematics education on junior high school is at a low level (386 score), lower than the previous year (397 score) so that deliver Indonesia on the order of 38 among 45 countries. The low achievement reflects the achievements of content aspect and cognitive aspect of students. Content aspect includes numbers, algebra, geometry, along with data and probability. Meanwhile, cognitive aspect includes knowledge, application and reasoning. With a maximum score of 100, Indonesian students were only able to achieve a score of 24 for the number, 22 for algebra, 24 for geometry, and 29 for data and probability. While cognitive achievement percentages are respectively 35% knowledge achievement, 40% application achievement and 25% reasoning achievement. With these results, it seems that Indonesian students have difficulty in solving mathematics problem. Moreover, Indonesian students are also weak in terms of knowledge, application, and reasoning in mathematics.

The above facts, shows that our students more emphasis on reading, writing and calculating ability (*calistung*). If the ability which required is only calculating and the exam's questions is massively, asking more about calculation or procedural ability, then our students will be more concerned with the final outcome of the process. They might even ignore thinking ability. The importance of students to think has been seeded in the mathematics learning objectives curriculum in 2006 that is to train how to think and reason in drawing conclusions through research, experiment, showing similarities, differences and consistencies and inconsistencies (Depdiknas, 2006). The matching with the curriculum in 2006, NCTM (2000) formulate mathematics learning objectives namely: (a) mathematical communication, (b) mathematical reasoning, (c) mathematical problem solving, (d) (mathematical connections, and (e) positive attitudes toward mathematics. Remembering that thinking skill is one of the important aspects in learning mathematics, so the study of students' thinking on mathematics problems needs to be studied.

Thinking is the process of obtaining information, processing information, storing information, and recalling information that is controlled by the brain (Slavin, 1997). Thinking occurs when a person is currently faced with a complex problem that requires a solution. In addition, the opinion Krulick & Rudnick (1995) show that thinking can be divided into four categories, namely recall, basic, critical and creative. The lowest level of thinking according to (Krulick & Rudnick, 1995) is recalling. This thinking character is reflective that is recalling the concept or mathematical formulas,

for example $5 + 2 = 7$. The next level of thinking is the ability to understand mathematics concepts so that the concepts can be applied to solve the problems encountered. The next stage is critical thinking. This thinking process is thinking that can correlate and evaluate appropriate strategies to be used in solving the problems. Similar disclosed Prayitno, Subanji, & Muksar (2016) and Prayitno, Sutawidjaja, Subanji, & Muksar (2014) identified that critical thinking is marked by the process of constructing and evaluating the solving strategies to be used in solving the problems. The last thinking process is creative thinking. This thinking process produce the new and original final outcome.

Thinking undertaken by students is often reflected on completion result. Therefore, thinking that is done by students in solving mathematics problem can be seen from their behavior in form of assignment completion result (Prayitno, 2015, 2016). Moreover, thinking can be explored through the work result of students in constructing and solving mathematics problem (Subanji & Nusantara, 2013). To be able to explore the students' thinking, thing that needed is knowledge on how to portray students' thinking. In their research result (Gutiérrez, Jaime, & Fortuny, 1991) explain that *cognitive map/cognitive style* can be used to study in depth about the uniqueness of thinking process. It shows that by using a cognitive map the students' thinking method in solving mathematics problem can be explored.

Some researchers explore students' thinking process by using a cognitive map. From the research's results showed that cognitive map can describe the causality of phenomena and concepts also can be modeled (Pena, Sossa, & Gutierrez, 2007); Cognitive map can be used as a guide to get to the next step in order to obtain directions to think further (Jacobs & Schenk, 2003); *cognitive style* or *thinking style* is used as a mediator to the students' work in solving geometry problems with the theory of Van Hiele (Perdikaris, 2011); and cognitive map can be used to explore student's mistakes in constructing mathematical concepts (Subanji & Nusantara, 2013).

Cognitive map or also called as *cognitive mapping* is a technique for representing how the subject thinks about a certain problem or situation, so that researchers can have a certain attitude for the next step (Ackermann, Eden, Cropper, & Cropper, 2004). Cognitive map is a person's perspective on the subject, which is qualitatively described by the concept which is connected to be able to predict the causality behavior. Therefore, students' thinking process in solving mathematics problem can be explored by using a cognitive map. Cognitive map or *Cognitive map* can be described as follow.

Figure 1.The Model of Cognitive Map (Pena et al., 2007)

RESEARCH METHODS

This study explored the students' thinking in solving mathematics problem using a cognitive map. Therefore, this study is classified as descriptive qualitative study. Subjects of the study were junior high school students of IX grade which scattered in Malang namely SMPN 21 Malang, SMP Al Kautsar, and SMPN 1 Jabung and SMP SKJ Jabung. The subjects were choose because the subject had studied the material of statistics. The instrument was in form of the story problem in the context of decision-making about ranking. The instrument used in this study was an instrument that was adopted from the previous studies (Doerr & English, 2003). The following instrument was given at the time of data collection.

<i>Customers' Satisfaction Problem in a Restaurant</i>						
<i>Observe the table!</i>		<i>Fries</i>	<i>Burger</i>	<i>Kids Meal</i>	<i>Quickness</i>	<i>Chocolate Sundae</i>
<i>Your task is to</i>	<i>Customer 1</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>order the</i>	<i>Customer 2</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>menus from the</i>	<i>Customer 3</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>most liked one</i>	<i>Customer 4</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>to the most</i>	<i>Customer 5</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>disliked one by</i>	<i>Customer 6</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>
<i>customers!</i>	<i>Customer 7</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>2</i>
<i>Give your</i>	<i>Customer 8</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>explanation to</i>	<i>Customer 9</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>the answers.</i>	<i>Customer 10</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>3</i>

Figure 2. Problem of decision making (Doerr & English, 2003)

Data collection began with giving an instrument to the students to be solved by raising their voice. This method is known as *think aloud* (Samkof, Lai, & Weber, 2012). Researcher recorded the verbal expression and recorded the behavior of the students, including the unique things that subjects did when solving the problems. When one student finished, researcher did the same for other students until obtained the desired subject. The process of selecting subjects performed until obtained saturation of the data, it means appear the same or remains characteristics of several subjects for each characteristic.

RESULTAND DISCUSSION

Some research findings on the subjects in solving problem is obtained as follows, (1) the result answers by subjects from 5 schools had almost the same characteristics of answer and (2) solving strategies that used including sum, average, correlating the score with the ranking and *Talley* method. Based on the solving strategies, the researcher conducted an analysis to the results of students' work. Subjects who used the sum strategy referred as the subjects 1 (S1), subjects used the *Talley* strategy

referred as the subjects 2 (S2), subjects used the average strategy referred as the subjects 3 (S3), and subjects who used correlating score and ranking strategy referred as the subjects 4 (S4). The following are explanation of analysis result of subjects' works.

Analysis result of the subjects 1 (S1) to the answer with the sum strategy.

The following is one work results by S1 with sum up the ranking on each menu.

Jenis Makanan	Jumlah ranking
Fries	22
Burger	27
Quickness	29
Chocolate Sundae	35
Kids meal	37

Figure 3. The work result by S1 with sum up the rankings on each menu

Based on work result, S1 performed addition operation on each menu. The rankings on each menu summed up and the result as in the table. However, the process of how the S1 get ideas for summing takes a long time, when asked by researcher, S1 answered " I have nothing on my mind, about what I want to do", after that, researcher continued to monitor developments of S1 on solving the problem, until finally S1 tried to sum all rankings on each menu. Researcher asked, "how did you do it?" Then the student answered "... because there are digits on the table, so I tried to sum up the digits...". This shows that the S1 experienced reflective thinking. In this case, when students are faced with digits, they will always try so the digits can be operated. The thinking method of S1 often happens at the other students. When students are given a problem in form of digits and having collision, they will always tend to operated it. The situation that carried out by S1 is the existence of idea that each digit can be operated such as added, divided, multiplied, or subtracted.

The next process, S1 realized that the sum which has done still need to be replaced in form of ranking. As explained by S1 in an interview "...after I summed up all digits, i gave each sum a ranking. The least sum I gave first rank because the least digit on that table is ranking 1". Here is the overall result of students' answer.

Jenis Makanan	Jumlah ranking	Peringkat
Fries	22	1
Burger	27	2
Quickness	29	3
Chocolate Sundae	35	4
Kids meal	37	5

② Jumlah ranking ditambah dan yang hasilnya paling sedikit maka itu adalah peringkat yang pertama.

Figure 4. The work result by S1 correlating sum and ranking

Responses from S1 in this interview, is trying to uncover the existence of relation between sum and ranking. In this case, S1 correlate between sum and ranking. So from the responses, the students conclude that the lesser the sum of ranking on the menu, the higher the ranking will be. If researcher review on the concept of thought (Prayitno, 2016), so the process experienced by S1 is critical thinking. In this case, students correlate the sum of ranking with sequence patterns, thus bring up a new ranking to the sum of ranking. The following is thinking process by S1 when portrayed using a cognitive map.

Figure 5. The thinking process by S1 using a cognitive map.

Analysis result of the subjects 2 (S2) to the answer with the Talley strategy.

The following is one of work results by S2 using *Talley* method on each menu.

Fries = 1 =	K. M = 1 =	CH = 1 =
2 =	2 =	2 =
3 =	3 = -	3 =
4 =	4 =	4 =
5 = -	5 = ()	5 =
Burger 1 =	QK = 1 =	
2 =	2 =	
3 =	3 =	
4 =	4 =	
5 =	5 =	

Figure 6. Thinking process by S2 with *Talley* strategy

Based on the work result, S2 performed frequency grouping based on the total of customers by using *Talley* method. The thinking process by S2, began with trying out to recall solving strategy on previous problems (data processing). In this case, S2

interpreted the total of customers who choose the menu using frequency. For example, there are three customers who like fries menu most, that is interpreted by (1: III). Each ranking then compared on each menu. From five menus, fries got the first rank, because there are many customers who like fries most, more than the other menus. If there are the same frequencies on the same ranking on each menu, then S2 compared the total of frequencies on the previous rank (ranking 1). This is consistent with statement S2 expressed in work. Because there are the same frequencies on ranking 2 on two menus namely burger and chocolate sundae, so it can be seen from the other priorities that is the total of frequencies on the ranking 1. Here are the reasons of S2 when determining ranking 2.

Ranking 2 ada 2 pilihan antara Burger dan Chocolate sundae dan yang merampati ranking 2 adalah burger karena lebih banyak pelanggan menggunakan burger di ranking 1

Figure 7. Reason by S2 in determining the menu that get ranking 2

Based on interview to the students in determining the ranking 2 "... To determine the ranking 2, I examined the total of frequency on ranking 1 of burger and CS. Because the frequency on ranking 1 of burger more than CS, so I choose burger over chocolate sundae ". From the S2's answers, it is obtained S2's finding choose burger over CS as ranking 2, S2 was trying to find the association of total frequencies on burger and CS with each previous frequencies. The previous frequencies when determining the ranking 2, made as consideration to choose between two menus for the second rank. In this case, S2 associate frequencies on the menu with the previous frequencies so that the previous frequencies could be used as consideration to get the answer. The analogue process happened when S2 determine the third rank of each menu.

In determining the ranking 3, S2 tried to use elimination system on one of the menus because the menu has gotten ranking 2. In determining the ranking 3, S2 found the total of frequency on ranking 3, so obtained 2 menus namely burger and Quickness. The following is quote by S2, "... because the burger has gotten ranking 2, so Quickness get the ranking 3". Thinking conducted by S2, using the elimination that is eliminate the burger menu because it has gotten ranking 2. So S2, bringing up aspects of associating ranking 2 and 3. Furthermore, the total of frequencies also used to determine the ranking 4 and 5.

When viewed from the concept (Prayitno, 2016), it appears that S2 experienced critical thinking and occur the reconstruction of new knowledge in determining the ranking of the menu when there are the same ranking. In this case, students correlate the frequencies of the previous ranking, which bring up the appropriate decision. The following is thinking process by S2 when portrayed using a cognitive map.

Figure 8. The thinking process by S2 using cognitive map

Analysis result of the subjects 3 (S3) to the answer with the average strategy.

The analysis result to answer by S3 using average method has the similarity with work result by S1 using sum method. The following work result by S3 on solving mathematics problem using average method.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Mean Fries} &= \frac{(1.3) + (2.4) + (3.1) + (4.2)}{10} \\
 &= \frac{3 + 8 + 3 + 8}{10} = \frac{22}{10} = 2,2 \\
 \text{Mean Burger} &= \frac{(1.2) + (2.2) + (3.4) + (4.1) + (5.1)}{10} \\
 &= \frac{2 + 4 + 12 + 4 + 5}{10} = \frac{27}{10} = 2,7 \quad MB \\
 \text{Mean KidsMeal} &= \frac{(1.2) + (2.1) + (4.2) + (5.5)}{10} \\
 &= \frac{2 + 2 + 8 + 25}{10} = \frac{37}{10} = 3,7 \\
 \text{Mean Quickness} &= \frac{(1.2) + (2.1) + (3.4) + (4.2) + (5.1)}{10} \\
 &= \frac{2 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 5}{10} = \frac{29}{10} = 2,9 \\
 \text{Mean Chocolate suricee} &= \frac{1 + (2.2) + 3 + (4.3) + (5.3)}{10} \\
 &= \frac{1 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 15}{10} = \frac{35}{10} = 3,5
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 9. Work result by S3 using the average strategy

Based on work result, S3 solved by finding the mean (average) on each menu. Average finding process conducted by S3, has often done when confronted with the form of the above problem. Researcher said "how did you use average method?", and then S3 explained "... I remember about the material on statistics, so I use the concept of mean, i find the average of each menu" then "... I associate with the total of ranking and the ranking, after that I divide it by 10 because there are 10 customers?"

Furthermore, researcher tried to ask again "why not divided by 5?", Then S3 reiterated the reason "... according to this problem, something that need to be find is which menu the customer like most, then cause I summed up the digits on each menu, so I divided it by the total that aim sum", so that from work result obtained unequal average among 5 menus. Furthermore, S3 associated the average with the ranking. Menu that had the lowest average was given the highest rank (ranking 1) which further ranked till ranking 5. The thinking process conducted by S3 began with finding average on each menu, which then recreated the rankings based on the average. If thinking structure viewed by cognitive map, then the thinking process of S3 is as follows.

Figure 10. The thinking process by S3 using cognitive map

Analysis result of the subjects 4 (S4) to the answer with the scoring and ranking strategies.

The work result by S4 has similarity with S2 which using *Talley* strategy, but there are some differences. Based on the work results of S4, the student performed frequency grouping based on the total customers using *Talley* method. Interview result on the subject is "... collected how many customers were choosing the menu .." then "... I wrote, as it was based on experience of working on such matters, I wrote in like this ". From S4's responses to the *Talley* strategy, S4 try to recall the context that

S4 has with the problem encountered. The work method done by the S4, has similarity with S1. However S4, continued the next step didn't see the previous frequency as on S1.

In this case, S4 try to do reflection on the solution of the problem. Reflection that revealed is S4 knowledge to perform data calculations by *Talley* method. Here is the work result of S4 using *Talley*.

F = ⑤: 1111 = 15	A = 1: 11 = 10	KM = 1: 11 = 10
②: 111 = 12	2: 1 = 4	2: 1 = 4
③: 1 = 3	3: 1111 = 12	3: 0 = 0
④: 11 = 8	4: 11 = 4	4: 11 = 4
⑤: 0 = 38	5: 1 = 1	5: 1111 = 5
	31	23
B = 1: 11 = 10	CS = 1: 1 = 5	
2: 11 = 8	2: 11 = 8	
3: 1111 = 12	3: 1 = 3	
4: 1 = 2	4: 111 = 8	
5: 1 = 1	5: 111 = 3	
33	27	

Figure 11. Work result of S4 with *Talley* strategy which associated with the score and ranking

Furthermore, on the work result of S4 explicitly write the highest rank (ranking 1) was given a score of 5, and so on until the ranking 5 was given a score of 1. Based on the work result, S4 tried to multiply the score by the ranking. Furthermore, the product of the score and the ranking on each menu are summed up. This thinking method of S4 is associating between the rankings and the scores, in this case the total ranking multiplied by the score. If on the first rank, then it multiplied by the score of 5 and so on.

Based on interviews with the S4 obtained "... I gave point or score to every ranking I gave 5 to the ranking 1, and so on. Next I summed up the products of ranking 1 to 5, from that way I found the solution... ". What has been done by S4 is a reverse order, so that the best ranking has the highest score. Here are the reasons delivered by S4.

Dijelasakan
 Jikalau setiap ranking diberi poin, maka per ranking 1 = 5,
 2 = 4, 3 = 3, 4 = 2, 5 = 1, setelah itu, setiap poin dikalikan
 dengan jumlah ranking, dan akan terdapat data
 seperti di no: 1, dan dapat diketahui alasan utama
 pengunjung mengunjungi McD adalah Fries, yang ke:
 burger, ke 3: Quikness, ke 4: cho colate sundae, dan ya
 ke 5 adalah Kids Meal

Figure 12. Reasoning by S4 when making decision about food menus

The work result done by S4 is a combination of frequencies (S2) and the sum of scores (S1), but S4 work using the reverse order. If in S1 is based on the least sum, but on the S4 is based on the most sum. So it can be said as reverse order. In this case, S4 try to associate between scores and rankings, so that the sum of each menu can be used as consideration to bring up the rankings on the menus. The following is thinking process by S4 when portrayed using a cognitive map.

Figure 13. The thinking process by S4 using cognitive map

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There are four strategies used by subjects in solving mathematics problem about rankings: a) the sum strategy, b) Talley strategy, c) the average strategy and d) correlation between the score and ranking strategy. In addition, the thinking process that occurred in each subject undergoing a process of critical thinking, this is indicated by when the subject gained menu with the same ranking, so that subjects seek other alternative that used as consideration to make a decision. In this case, the subjects correlate between the rankings and scores in deciding the menu on the same ranking. Further studies on the thinking process and cognitive map is a cognitive map can explore the thinking mistake location, characteristics of thinking and construction process of students' understanding in mathematics problem.

REFERENCES

- Ackermann, F., Eden, C., Cropper, S., & Cropper, S. (2004). Getting Started with Cognitive Mapping. In *The 7th Young OR Conference* (pp. 1–14). University of Warwick. Retrieved from <http://www.banxia.com/pdf/de/GettingStartedWithCogMapping.pdf>
- Depdiknas. (2006). *Standar Kompetensi dan Kompetensi Dasar Matematika SMP/MTs*. Jakarta: Depdiknas.
- Doerr, H. M., & English, L. (2003). A modeling perspective on students' mathematical reasoning about data. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 34(2), 110–136.
- Gutiérrez, A., Jaime, A., & Fortuny, J. M. (1991). An Alternative Paradigm To Evaluate the Acquisition of the Van Hiele Levels. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 22(3), 237–251. <http://doi.org/10.2307/749076>
- Jacobs, L. F., & Schenk, F. (2003). Unpacking the Cognitive Map: The Parallel Map Theory of Hippocampal Function. *Psychological Review*, 110(2), 285–315. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.110.2.285>
- Krulick, S., & Rudnick, J. A. (1995). *The New Sourcebook for Teaching and Problem Solving in Elementary School* (6th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- NCTM. (2000). Principles and Standards for School Mathematics. *School Science and Mathematics*, 47(8), 868–279. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1949-8594.2001.tb17957.x>
- Pena, A., Sossa, H., & Gutierrez, A. (2007). Cognitive Maps: an Overview and their Application for Student Modeling. *Computación Y Sistemas*, 10(3), 230–250. Retrieved from <http://www.scielo.org.mx/pdf/cys/v10n3/v10n3a4.pdf>
- Perdikaris, S. C. (2011). Using the Cognitive Styles to Explain an Anomaly in the Hierarchy of the van Hiele Levels. *Journal of Mathematical Sciences & Mathematics Education*, 6(2), 35–43. Retrieved from <http://msme.us/2011-2-5.pdf>
- Prayitno, A. (2015). *Proses Berpikir refraktif Mahasiswa dalam Menyelesaikan Masalah Matematika*. Disertasi tidak dipublikasikan. Program Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Malang.
- Prayitno, A. (2016). The Characteristics of Students' Refractive Thinking about Data. In M. S. Dr. Warsono (Ed.), *Proceeding of 3rd International Conference On Research, Implementation And Education Of Mathematics And Science (ICRIEMS)* (p. ME.29-ME.38). Yogyakarta: UNY.
- Prayitno, A., Subanji, & Muksar, M. (2016). Refractive Thinking with Dual Strategy in Solving Mathematics Problem. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education Ver. III*, 6(3), 49–56. <http://doi.org/10.9790/7388-0603034956>
- Prayitno, A., Sutawidjaja, A., Subanji, & Muksar, M. (2014). Construction Theory of Critical Thinking As Process Towards Refraction Thinking In Mathematics. In *Proceedings of International Seminar*.
- Samkof, A., Lai, Y., & Weber, K. (2012). On The Different Ways That Mathematicians Use Diagrams In Proof Construction. *Research in Mathematics Education*, 14(1), 49–67. <http://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14794802.2012.657438>

Slavin, R. E. (1997). *Educational psychology: Theory and practice*. Allyn Bacon Inc (Vol. 612).

Subanji, & Nusantara, T. (2013). Karakterisasi Kesalahan Berpikir Siswa Dalam Mengonstruksi Konsep Matematika. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 19(2), 208–217. <http://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.17977/jip.v19i2.4215>

Yuwono, I. (2009). *Membumikan Pembelajaran Matematika Di Sekolah*. Malang.

